

NEW APPLICATIONS FOR INJECTION MOLDED

GRAPHITE FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

Richard C. James
General Manager
Keithley Custom Molding
A Division of Keithley Instruments, Inc.
Cleveland, Ohio

Introduction

In a broad sense, graphite fiber reinforced thermoplastics can be considered as materials with properties approaching those of metals but having the processability of plastics. They replace conventional plastic materials when some desirable property of metal is lacking. They usually replace metals, however, not when some desirable property of a plastic material is lacking but when the labor cost component of a metal part is high.

Because of the relatively high unit cost of graphite fiber reinforced materials, it is often some unique combination of mechanical and physical properties that makes these materials attractive or cost effective for certain applications. In the three applications that will be reviewed, the combinations of property requirements and cost that make graphite fiber reinforced parts attractive will be discussed. All three parts have been made by injection molding, the most economical method of fabrication for these parts.

Ion Chamber Housings

The calibration of X-ray equipment has become more important and demanding in recent years. One method of calibration is the use of an ion chamber dosimeter. X-radiation has been historically measured in terms of the ionization effect a beam produces in air. "Ideal" or free air chambers are generally unsuitable for field service due to their size and weight making them non-portable devices.

Practical or approximately "ideal" portable ion chambers must have an "air equivalent" response to X-rays and electrical conductivity as well as dimensional stability.

The Roentgen, or standard unit of X-ray exposure measurement, is defined in terms of the ionization caused by an X-ray beam in air. A practical ion chamber used in X-ray dosimetry must be constructed from a material which reacts to X-ray exposure as if it were made from air. The chamber material must create a situation known as "electron equilibrium" with respect to an equivalent mass of air, as well as respond to various beam intensities the same way that air does. The behavior of a material exposed to X-rays depends more on the atomic number than on chemical composition. Plastic materials are generally suitable because they are largely composed of carbon ($Z=6$) which is reasonably close to nitrogen ($Z=7$) and oxygen ($Z=8$), the major components of the atmosphere. Graphite fiber, which provides electrical conductivity in this application, is also composed of carbon ($Z=6$).

Mathematical relationships are available to calculate the theoretical atomic number of a composite. Small variations in the molecular composition of the thermoplastic matrix materials were found to have significant effects on the atomic number of a composite and thus on the air equivalence of the chamber. However, theoretically well behaved materials did not always produce a flat chamber response with respect to effect of beam energy. (See Figure 1) Some experimentation with different matrix materials was undertaken and good results were obtained with graphite fiber reinforced polyester.

In this application, dimensional consistency and dimensional stability were important in that the volume of air inside the chamber must be held constant with time and also from part to part in order to reduce the time and expense involved in calibration.

Considerable savings in cost was accrued through the use of an injection molded chamber, even though chambers are made in relatively low volume compared to most thermoplastic injection molded parts. Previously each chamber had been machined from a solid block of a plastic material then coated with a carbon based material in order to provide surface electrical conductivity.

Rolls for Textile and Paper Processing Equipment

Covered rolls are used widely in the textile and paper industries. These structures are subjected to a cyclic loading which in turn causes a temperature rise in thermoplastic covering. The amount of the temperature rise is dependent upon strain levels and frequency. As the covering materials become warm, mechanical properties change and the material being processed in between the

covered roll and another roll will thus see different pressures and be processed in a different manner than material processed prior to the rise in temperature.

The high thermal conductivity of graphite fiber reinforced thermoplastics reduce the temperature rise in materials subjected to cyclic loading. The heat generated in the graphite fiber reinforced thermoplastic is conducted away to the support structure. The resulting lower temperature rise in the material introduces smaller changes in the mechanical properties. The thermal conductivity of graphite fiber allows the use of thermoplastic materials for structural members subjected to high frequency loading since the properties will not change appreciably under the cyclic loading conditions. In some applications this can mean an increase in process speed with no effect on the quality of product being processed. Figure 2 shows a cross section of a graphite fiber reinforced thermoplastic "covered" roll.

Fishing Reel Cages

The outer portion of a fly fishing reel is called a "cage." As Figure 3 shows, the cage has "windows" (through which the line travels), and supports the spindle (on which the spool revolves) as well as other springs and pawls which are components of the drag mechanism. The cage is attached to a "foot" which is used in turn for attachment of the reel to a fishing rod.

Fly fishing reels have generally been made with cast aluminum cages. Both light weight and resistance to corrosion are desirable for cages. The raw castings are machined and the spindle and other components riveted on. The spindle used with aluminum cages is generally made of steel. The spindle provides both a bearing surface for the spool and also acts as a cantilever support for the spool. In most cages, an exceptionally thick section is required in the area where the spindle is supported.

The outer rim of the cage has a stiffness requirement which overrides the strength requirements for most materials. The stiffness requirement is that an angler, particularly one with a trout on the other end of his line, cannot squeeze the rim to the point at which it interferes with the free movement of the spool. (Note: most fly fishermen do not grasp the spool with one hand and reel in with the other -- however, this condition does occur.)

An injection molded graphite fiber reinforced thermoplastic cage with a molded in spindle has several advantages compared to an aluminum casting with a steel spindle.

1. As the specific stiffness of the composite approaches that of aluminum, the cage weighs far less than an aluminum casting.
2. The spindle weighs less than the steel spindle by a factor of five.
3. The spindle does not require lubrication because of the natural lubricity of the material.
4. The labor cost in fastening the spindle and other bosses to the cage body is eliminated. The possibility for error and thus scrap is also eliminated.
5. No secondary anodizing or painting operations are required. The cage and spindle are corrosion resistant and have a good "as molded" surface finish.
6. The back of the cage is smooth and flat. No rivets show and there is no thick section protrusion to support the spindle.
7. The cage is much less likely to break when dropped.

Overall, the objectives of a lower weight cage with an excellent appearance and structural properties superior to those of an aluminum cast cage have been met. Furthermore, the processing efficiencies of injection molding are such that even with the relatively high cost of the material, a competitive cost to the previous method was achieved.

Figure 1
Chamber Response versus Beam Energy

FIGURE 2. SECTION OF GRAPHITE FIBER REINFORCED
THERMOPLASTIC COVERED ROLL.

Figure 3. Fishing Reel Cage

DISCUSSION/Session 5A

COMMENT: J.H. Underwood, U.S. Army Benet Weapons Lab

The "different philosophy" mentioned by Dr. Salkind for understanding fracture of composites is verified by the increase in residual strength noted in our tests of notched glass-epoxy with increasing number of prior fatigue cycles. This opposite effect, to that of metals, can be explained by the nature of the notch-tip fatigue damage.

COMMENT: C. Zweben, Du Pont Experimental Station, Wilmington, Delaware

Simplified models, such as the one developed by Kelly for discontinuous fibers, have been shown to be useful for understanding the behavior of composites. The Rapporteur has done a disservice to the authors using such models by dismissing their papers out of hand because they have not used a three-dimensional elasticity approach.

COMMENT: Y. Lindblom, Linkoping, Sweden

Dr. Tsai doubted the relevance of applying a simple linear weight rule when calculating the strength of a composite from the volume fractions of components such as fiber and matrix.

With the exception of tungsten carbide composites, most two-phase or multiphase metal structures have strengths which generally cannot be described by linear relationships to volume fractions. The structure of a plain carbon steel consists of α -iron phase, ferrite

and a carbide eutectoid, pearlite, and at 0.9°C carbon the structure contains 100% pearlite. The relationship between yield strength and volume fractions of ferrite and pearlite is approximately as described in Fig. 1.

Regarding ferrite as matrix the first increments of pearlite contribute more to the yield strength of the material than subsequently added increments. A reasonable allowance for this can be achieved by exponentiating the volume fraction of pearlite so that the contribution of pearlite to the yield strength of the steel is given by an equation as follows:

$$\sigma_p = \beta \cdot V_p^n \quad \text{where}$$

σ_p = contribution of pearlite to yield strength

β = proportionality constant

n = interaction exponent giving a measure of how increasing amounts of pearlite contribute to the yield strength.

If the total yield strength of the carbon steel is given as the sum of the contributions of ferrite and pearlite, one obtains

$$\sigma_{\text{total}} = \alpha \cdot V_F + \beta \cdot V_p^n = \alpha \cdot V_F + \beta(1-V_F)^n$$

as $V_F + V_p = 1$ where α is a proportionality constant and V_F the volume fraction of ferrite.

The above equation is applicable for many two-phase metallic compounds. If the weight rule applies, n is equal to unity. If the flow stresses for given strains are known, α and β can be replaced by the flow stress equations and a relation between stresses and strains can be obtained. The described relationship is naturally orientation dependent and represents a uniaxial load situation.

QUESTION: A.R. Bunsell, Sussex University, England

What evidence is there for synergistic effects in hybrids? Advantage comes from change in load searing behavior, but this is not a synergistic effect on properties.

ANSWER: S. Tsai, Air Force Materials Lab, Dayton, Ohio

Hybrid composites are expected to behave in a fashion similar to laminated composites with multidirectional plies. Synergistic effects of hybrids beyond the simple model of parallel springs can occur from (2) sources:

1. Post first-ply failure can be modeled by a partial failure scheme such that the failed layer is not completely destroyed.

This scheme has been successfully applied to laminates of multi-directional plies by Hahn and Tsai in Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 8 (1974), p. 288.

2. Initial stresses exist because of differences in thermomechanical constants among hybrid plies. Such stresses may have beneficial effects on first-ply and ultimate failures. The change in first-ply failure stresses in carbon/glass hybrids by Bunsell and Harris, Composites, Vol. 5 (1974), p. 157, may be the result of this initial stress.

Synergistic effects due to chemical interaction can occur in addition to the mechanical interaction. Evaluation of benefits of hybrids must also include compression and biaxial loads. Intuitively, hybrids make sense if the matching fiber has lower strength but higher strain; they make no sense to match fibers with equal strains. Similar constraints for matching constituent properties can be developed from the viewpoints of thermomechanical compatibility, a balance between tensile and compressive properties or improved dynamic property. Only with proper matching can synergistic benefits be derived.

QUESTION: Mr. Gruber, Ciba-Geigy, Basle, Switzerland

Did you really not find a difference in wear whether the C-fibers were perpendicular or in the plane of friction? Any explanation for this phenomenon? Did the friction coefficient correspond to the one of graphite or to silver?

ANSWER: M.F. Amateau, The Aerospace Corp., Los Angeles, Calif.

The wear rates for both PAN-based and rayon-based fibers were indeed unaffected by the orientation of the fiber for up to 20 minutes of sliding at loads to 16 N, as shown in Fig. 8 of the paper. The effect of fiber orientation on friction was somewhat unclear. It appears that the wear behavior of these metal matrix composites is significantly influenced by the size and nature of the wear debris and not on the geometric details of the initial fiber contact. The initial dislodging of wear debris should indeed be sensitive to fiber-orientation, however, two conditions existing in these experiments may have masked this effect. First, wear rates were measured after one or two minutes of sliding which may be sufficient to initiate significant fiber fracture regardless of orientation. Second, it must be noted that both the fabrication of the composite and the nature of the starting graphite yarns contribute to some degree of off-axis geometry, thus reducing the difference between the nominal orientations.

The coefficient of friction values are related to load, sliding time, fiber type and matrix composition, but little correlation

exists between friction and fiber orientation. Rayon precursor composites loaded to 6N resulted in friction values approaching those of graphite while that of PAN fiber composites approached those of the metal matrix.

QUESTION: K.K. Chawla, Inst Militar de Engenharia, Rio de Janeiro

You showed a slide of B/A1 fan blades where midspan shrouds have been eliminated. Are they in actual use?

ANSWER: M.J. Salkind, AVCO, Lowell, Massachusetts

No. They are developmental, but will be flight tested in 1975 on the Pratt and Whitney TF-30 engine on the F-111D aircraft.

QUESTION: L.M. Palenzona, ESTEC, Holland

Not much has been heard about pressure vessels applications of advanced composites - design criteria, reliability, test etc., choice of fibers and matrices, methods of analysis, future potentials for advanced composites. Is there any information?

ANSWER: M.J. Salkind

My knowledge of recent pressure vessel applications is limited; however, I am aware of experimental work with boron, graphite, and KevlarTM fibers for pressure vessels. Motivation for using high modulus materials is better modulus match with metal liners. Higher structural efficiency is also an obvious motivation.

QUESTION: W. Bishop, Ciba-Geigy (UK), Duxford, Cambridge

Since pressures are on to simplify sandwich panel fabrication with advanced composite skins and cure these skins directly to the cone in one bonding operation, what is the influence of this non-perfect fibre alignment array? I would like to know if the authors have any results to indicate the influence of this "one-shot" process on strength and stiffness characteristics of the laminate.

ANSWER: O. Ishai, Technion, Haifa

A small number of specimens were prepared from the same batch of material by the "one shot method." They were tested in compression by the same sandwich beam flexure method described. Results indicated a substantial drop (about 50%) in compressive strength of the facing prepared by the "one shot method" compared to those prepared by the "two shot method." This drop may be attributed to the poorer fiber alignment and straightness obtained by the "one shot method."

DESIGNING FOR NON-STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS
AND CONTINUATION TO SESSION 4
ON PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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